

Scores Obtained by Criterion and Category: Criteria of relevance and appropriateness																
Primary studies	Paper	Criterion													TOTAL	
		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13		
PS1	Towards Automated Detection of Inline Code Comment Smells	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	11.5	
PS2	Automated Inline Comment Smell Detection and Repair with LLMs	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	12.5	
PS3	Taxonomy of Inline Code Comment Smells	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	12.0	
PS4	Using Transformer-based Pre-trained Language Model for Automated Evaluation of Comments to Aid Software Maintenance	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	0	10.5	
PS5	Do automatic comment generation techniques fall short? Exploring the influence of method dependencies on code understanding	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	12.5	
PS6	Reliable Inline Code Documentation with LLMs: Fine-G	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	12.0	
PS7	Autogenics: Automated generation of context-aware inline comments for code snippets on programming Q&A sites using LLM	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	10.5	
PS8	Leveraging Language Models for Code Comment Classification	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	0	1	0.5	1	1	1	0.5	9.5	
PS9	An empirical study on the quality assessment of code comments generated by large language models for different programming paradigms	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	1	1	0.5	11.5	
PS10	Towards efficient code documentation: A dataset for automated comment generation in Java	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	1	0.5	10.0	
PS11	Automated code comments generation using large language models: Empirical evaluation of T5 and BART	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	1	0.5	0.5	11.0	
PS12	Deep code-comment understanding and assessment	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	11.0	
PS13	Detecting Inline Code Comment Smells Leveraging CodeBERT Model	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	10.5	
PS14	The CodeLLM Handshake: Smarter Maintenance Through AI	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1.0	1	1	1	12.0	

PS15	Suggesting Comment Completions for Python using Neural Language Models	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.5	10.0
PS16	An empirical study on the effectiveness of large language models for SATD identification and classification	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	10.0
PS17	LLMUpdater: Automatic comment synchronization via edit model guided LLMs	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	12.0
PS18	R ² ComSync: improving code-comment synchronization with in-context learning and reranking	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	13.0
PS19	Few-shot training LLMs for project-specific code-summarization	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	11.0
PS20	Adversarial Robustness of Deep Code Comment Generation	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	11.5
PS21	DLCoG: A Novel Framework for Dual-Level Code Comment Generation Based on Semantic Segmentation and In-Context Learning	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	11.0
PS22	Detecting Code Comment Inconsistencies using LLM and Program Analysis	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	10.5
PS23	Code Comment Classification with Data Augmentation and Transformer-Based Models	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	11.5
PS24	Less Is More: DocString Compression in Code Generation	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	12.5
PS25	SE OCD: Detecting obsolete code comments by fusing semantic features and expert features	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	12.0
PS26	Large Language Models are Few-Shot Summarizers: Multi-Intent Comment Generation via In-Context Learning	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	12.0
PS27	A comparative study on method comment and inline comment	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	10.5
PS28	DocChecker: Bootstrapping Code Large Language Model for Detecting and Resolving Code-Comment Inconsistencies	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	12.5
PS29	Snippet Comment Generation Based on Code Context Expansion	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	10.5
PS30	Retrieve and refine: exemplar-based neural comment generation	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0.5	0.5	1	1	0.5	0.5	10.0
Criteria Total		1	0.8	1	1	1	1	0.6	0.9	0.7	1	1	0.8	0.6	11.3

Category	Score
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Clarity	0.9
Rigor	0.9
Relevancia	1.0
Credivily	0.7